

The Role of Social Media in Shaping Misconceptions of Feminism: The Case Study of Indonesia Media on X

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Abstract.

This research aims to examine the misconceptions surrounding feminism in the Indonesian context, particularly the tendency to conflate feminism with misandry. In a country where feminist discourse remains contested, such misunderstandings are posited to shape public perception. Therefore, a critical feminism approach in understanding how feminism is portrayed by the media. The three biggest media in Indonesia on platform X became the sample for this research, with a total of 48 articles examined. Content analysis is used as a method to produce a misconception rate; a way to quantify the perceived misconception of feminism throughout these media. The findings indicate that explicit misconceptions in media were relatively rare, since the majority of content observed was neutral in tone and presented in a straightforward, fact-based manner, with minimal interpretive or ideological framing. However, this may be attributed to the limited number of articles addressing the topic. Furthermore, there is a possibility that with the mixed deliveries of media on X, the misconception might not be featured explicitly in the articles, highlighting the need for further research.

Keywords: Feminism Misconceptions, Content Analysis, Indonesian Media, Misandry, Media Representation.

1 Background

Digital spaces are central to the emergence and definition of the fourth wave of feminism [1]. In the context of postfeminism, many young women have become increasingly aware of persistent gender inequalities, prompting renewed feminist activism characterized by online engagement. This wave marks the rise of "call-out

culture", where sexist and misogynistic behavior is being exposed and challenged through digital platforms. Among these, X (formerly known as Twitter) plays a prominent role as a text-based platform for feminist discourse and solidarity. Feminist campaigns often gain traction by vocally confronting misogyny, reflecting what Kitzinger [2] identifies as a social movement aimed at breaking the patriarchal structures and advocating for gender justice. As Earl and Kimport [3] assert, digital platforms significantly shape contemporary activism, enabling both collective and individual feminist expressions.

Since 2010, there has been a significant global surge in digital feminist activism, marked by the widespread use of blogs and social media platforms to raise awareness and critically engage with issues such as patriarchy, sexism, misogyny, gender-based violence, and systemic inequality. As platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Tumblr became increasingly accessible and widely adopted worldwide, they offered new avenues for feminist discourse and collective action. Hashtags such as #MooreandMe exemplified how social media could be strategically employed as powerful tools for feminist resistance and mobilization. By leveraging the participatory nature of digital platforms, feminists have been able to expand the reach of their movements, foster greater engagement, and create more inclusive, transnational spaces for dialogue and advocacy [1].

1.1 History of Feminism

Feminism started in 1837 with the intention of freeing the people, women and men, stated by Charles Fourier, a philosopher in France. Manisha Desai, an Indian-American sociologist defines feminism as a transnational movement that challenges power and inequality across borders, recognizing that gender justice is interconnected with struggles for racial, economic, and ecological justice.” Feminism has a lot of meaning from different viewpoints, for example, feminism can be described as “an idea and a social movement in favor to change the subordinate status of women in a society that prioritizes men” [4] while Angela Davis believes that feminism includes more than gender equality. It is also about fighting racism, capitalism, and imperialism. It’s a movement that calls for the transformation of society as a whole [5].

Definitions of feminism can be essentialized into a single meaning: to equalize the role of women and men in society and yet some people tend to associate it with negative connotations, such as having misandry-behavior, the stereotypical man-hating activists who believe that men are the cause of all problems [6]. Anderson [7] suggests that this negative stigma around feminist labels influenced both men

and women to not get behind the feminist movement, despite the original meaning behind it

Misandry is often expressed as negative stereotypes of the opposite sex, in this case, towards men. This perception is perceived as a culturally propagated hatred; which means it is reinforced and circulated through societal norms and media portrayals, often without critical examination and can lead to feminism movements backwards [8]. Social media played an impactful role in the evolution of feminism. For example, how women seem to connect and help each other through the platform of social media. Social media's algorithm is to promote high-emotional content in order to make their user stay longer on their site or application, adding to that, fact-checking on social media is very close to non-existence, thus making the spread of misinformation way easier and quicker [9].

Explosion of feminism in social media, especially post-pandemic, studies have shown that social media has a great role and impact in terms of shaping the mass's opinion and perception. For instance, Michael Chan et al, stated the changing media and information landscape allows young people to access and engage with political and social issues directly through social media, which now serves as the main news source for youth globally [20]. In Taiwan, 76% of individuals aged 18 to 24 receive news through social media platforms, underlining their role in shaping people's perception. Not only that, Marco Guerini's research has shown that social media content that is controversial and plays with people's emotions tends to go viral quicker and easier, thus making it easy for false information to fly around the internet [21].

The issue of widely spreading misinformation is rapidly increasing due to the lack of security of the internet and social media [22]. With a large amount of hoax information that is widespread, the public experiences tremendous confusion in distinguishing which informations are correct, and which is not. The lack of ability to distinguish information that is heavily spread among social media, may lead to misinformation and amplifying hoaxes, which ultimately affect how feminism is perceived and its association with misandry. Thus, it became important to uncover how social media plays a role in shaping the misconceptions associated with feminism movements.

2 Research Methodology

This essay will engage with content analysis on platform X regarding the spread of hoaxes towards feminism. [6] encourages future research to investigate the relation between different feminist beliefs and attitudes towards men. Therefore, it is crucial to examine how the content spread through platform X encourages the spread of hoaxes and misinformation regarding feminism, also correlating them with misandrist behavior.

Content analysis will be the chosen methodology for this study, building on its successful application in previous research on gender stereotypes in magazines [22]. This study adopts a critical perspective in applying content analysis, aiming to uncover how media discourse reflects and reinforces dominant power structures and ideological biases against feminist movements. This approach aligns with recent developments in critical content analysis, as discussed by Tesar (2022) [24], who argues that a critically framed methodology enables researchers to interrogate the socio-political implications embedded within media content that may appear neutral on the surface. This approach offers them comprehensive patterns of coverage, its prevalence, and positioning of the campaign in the media. It also helps to discover the tone and pattern of women's movement spread across a platform with whether it has some positive, negative, mixed/balanced, unclear positioning. Rooted in the framework of Harold et al. 1952, content analysis involves examining the frequency and patterns of content types. In this study, it will be used to analyze published articles in X, uncovering instances of misinformation or misconceptions, while also quantifying their potential impact.

Content analysis methods for this essay will be taking articles from the top 3 media trending on X, which are Kompas, Detikcom, and CNN Indonesia, that contain misinformation of feminism. Analyzing articles from the top 3 media trending on X are accountable to perform but have been criticized for their ambiguity in defining what counts as evidence of 'misinformation' of feminism. On the other hand, some believe the core of misinformation regarding feminism boils down to the 'third wave feminism'. The perception of the third wave is to push boundaries outside of the second wave rather than continuing [12]. Despite the insights, the third wave of feminism had overlooked other contributing factors to the misconception of feminism.

This essay analyzes 48 articles in total from 2023 to 2024. The one-year time frame is chosen to increase relevance among popular issues that surround feminism. The

articles are found through searching Indonesian keywords that are associated with feminism misconception. Such as *perempuan* (females), *feminisme* (feminism), *gerakan perempuan* (female movements).

3 Literature Review

Studies have highlighted the emergence of feminist movements across social media as a significant development [13] [15]. The shift of the fight for gender equality from physical spaces to digital platforms has fundamentally reshaped the discourse [14]. However, this transition has also given rise to contrasting movements within Indonesia's digital landscape. One such example is the anti-feminism account based in Indonesia (@Indonesiatanpafeminis.id), featured in Maryani's study, which actively resists feminist ideologies. This contrast underscores a critical tension: while the digital space offers a powerful platform to advance feminist causes and promote gender equality, it equally provides a fertile ground for opposing forces to challenge these ideals. Anti-feminist groups, through strategic use of digital media, may spread misconceptions about feminism, thereby distorting its objectives and hindering progress [15]. This duality of the digital space reflects the complex dynamics at play in the ongoing battle for gender equality.

Additionally, feminists in the Global South face a unique set of challenges shaped by deep association with cultural, religious, and political sentiments [16]. Kishwar et al. [16] argued that in India, numerous narratives persist that misrepresent feminism, often framing it in ways that could be exploited within the digital space. This study also highlights a trend toward gender-biased movements that may distort the aims of gender equality, thus, undermining the feminist cause. Although Kishwar's research is situated in the Indian context, it raises important questions about the extent to which similar dynamics are at play in Indonesia.

Indonesia has acquired an internet penetration rate of 79.5% [17]. With this widespread access to the internet, to over 200 million Indonesians, we can safely assume that Indonesians are likely exposed to global trends, including those related to feminism. Social media, therefore, plays a crucial role in shaping public knowledge, even through trends that may appear harmless. For instance, Salma and Leiliyanti [14] examined the 'Girl Math, Boy Math' trend, which highlights how certain trends can influence perceptions of feminism. Originally, 'Girl Math' was framed as a counterpoint to 'Boy Math', mocking male behaviors and critiquing societal misogyny. While this critique effectively underscores feminist themes,

Salma and Leiliyanti [14] caution that the trend's popularity could inadvertently blur the lines, turning 'Girl Math' into a tool that reinforces misandry, which contradicts the core goals of feminism. This tension between advancing feminist ideals and perpetuating misconceptions highlights the importance of critically examining such trends and their broader implications.

Building on the studies mentioned above, this research aims to explore how feminism is portrayed within Indonesia's social media landscape, with a particular focus on the misconceptions that surround it. Additionally, this study responds to the call for critical feminism, as suggested by Fitch [19], which suggests a deeper examination of the knowledge structures and production that shape feminism. To achieve this objective, the research will seek to answer the following questions:

How have the three largest media accounts on X contributed to misconceptions about feminism?

4 Results

Using a content-analysis approach, I collected articles from the three largest Indonesian news accounts on X, Detikcom, CNN Indonesia, and Kompas, each followed by more than 4 million users. To locate material relevant to misconceptions about feminism, I searched their feeds with the Indonesian keywords "feminisme," "perempuan," and "kesetaraan gender." In total, I retrieved 18,492 articles; 12,030 from Detikcom, 4,840 from CNN Indonesia, and 1,622 from Kompas. I then narrowed the sample to items published between January 2024 and January 2025 and removed duplicate or off-topic pieces. The final set of articles used in this study is summarized in the descriptive table below.

Table 1. Descriptive

Descriptive	
Total Article	48
Detikcom	23
CNN Indonesia	6
Kompas	19
Total Paragraphs Analyzed	474

For each article, I first identified every paragraph that conveyed an inaccurate or distorted view of feminist ideas. The misconception rate was then computed as the

ratio of these problematic paragraphs to the total number of paragraphs in the article. A higher rate indicates a denser concentration of misconceptions.

Beyond counting misconceptions, I coded the article's overall sentiment toward feminism, whether its framing was positive (supportive of feminist principles), mixed (balanced or ambivalent), negative (critical or dismissive), or unclear (no discernible stance). The sentiments are determined based on personal judgement, thus even though an article is framed as positive, it does not necessarily mean that it does not contain any form of misconception.

This dual-layer analysis captures both the frequency and the tone of misrepresentation. All article-level scores and sentiment labels are summarized in the table below, providing a concise overview of how each outlet's coverage may shape public understanding of feminism.

Table 2. Analysis

	Total Paragraphs	Amount of Paragraphs with Misconceptions	Average Misconception Rate
Detikcom			
Positive to Feminism	136	5	14%
Mixed	33	4	17%
Negative to Feminism	0	0	0%
Unclear	39	1	6
CNN Indonesia			
Positive to Feminism	36	1	11%
Mixed	0	0	0%
Negative to Feminism	0	0	0%
Unclear	20	0	0%
KOMPAS			
Positive to Feminism	113	4	11%
Mixed	18	3	18%
Negative to Feminism	11	0	0%
Unclear	59	0	0%

From the table, we could see that Detikcom has the highest average misconception despite having the highest positive sentiments. Partially because they have the largest amount of articles that are relevant to this research, but also how it represented the public perspective on feminism. Out of the 48 articles that I have analyzed, there are only 2 articles that clearly stated, feminism is not based on women hating men. Most of the articles only mentioned the existence of gender-biased issues and how we need an inclusive environment.

On the other hand, CNN Indonesia has the lowest average misconception, because they have the lowest articles published and most of the contents are displayed in videos, thus making it out of reach of this research.

Meanwhile for KOMPAS, the sentiments are also mixed. For example, while the title says *Pimpinan Tinggi Perempuan Diminta Ciptakan Kebijakan Memihak Wanita*, the contents say otherwise. While the title may feature misandry-values, the content itself explains that most of the public policies are more favorable for men, and the author reported that the women policy makers encourage the policies to make room for more gender-equal policies. Highlighting deeper research is needed on how media frames feminism both in its title and content.

The findings indicate that Indonesia's leading news accounts on X; Detikcom, CNN Indonesia, and Kompas rarely function as primary engines of feminist misconceptions. Isolated inaccuracies do appear, but overall misconception rates are low because most posts follow a straightforward, news-reporting style. Headlines, quotations, and concise event summaries dominate the coverage, leaving little opportunity for the editorial distortions that typically shape public opinion.

This "just-the-facts" framing means the outlets seldom adopt a strong stance on feminist issues. They mostly relay official statements, legal developments, or social-media trends with minimal interpretation, limiting their persuasive impact on readers' views of feminism. Their influence is further diluted by mixed-media formats such as short videos, infographics, and embedded clips that distract from the written text and disperse audience attention. With readers' focus divided across multiple modalities, a single paragraph's ability to shape attitudes is weakened, reinforcing these outlets' role as neutral conveyors of information rather than opinion leaders.

In conclusion, although some misconceptions about feminism do surface in these news feeds, mainstream media accounts on X contribute only modestly to shaping public misunderstanding. The larger drivers of feminist misconceptions likely lie

elsewhere, such as in opinion columns, influencer threads, or audience echo chambers rather than in the straight-news content produced by these accounts.

5 Discussion

In contrast to previous literature, such as the study by Maryani et al. [13], this research found a differing perspective. While Maryani et al. [13] emphasized that digital spaces can act as contested arenas where opposing forces challenge the ideals of feminist movements and gender equality, the Indonesian media discourse on platform X appears to function primarily as a neutral, fact-based environment. Rather than actively engaging in ideological debate, the general theme observed tends to report events or issues in a straightforward manner, without positioning itself in support of or opposition to feminist ideals. This suggests a more observational role within the digital space. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the kinds of challenges identified by Maryani et al. [13] may still manifest through other forms of digital content or on alternative platforms, and thus require further exploration.

This interpretation is further supported when considered alongside Yuewen's [15] findings, which highlight how anti-feminist groups use digital media to spread misconceptions about feminism, thereby challenging its core objectives. However, our analysis of the top three Indonesian media accounts on platform X did not show any indication of these anti-feminist digital strategies being reflected or amplified. In other words, these influential media outlets do not appear to be a target or a vehicle for the narratives described by Yuewen [15]. This reinforces the notion that platform X, at least through these dominant channels, serves a more neutral role rather than acting as a site of contestation. While Yuewen's [15] findings may still apply to other digital platforms or formats, such dynamics were not observed in the present study.

Finally, Fitch et al. [19] emphasize the importance of advancing critical feminist research, particularly within the Indonesian context, where such perspectives remain underrepresented. Building on this call, our research on the three most prominent media outlets on platform X reveals relatively few instances of feminist discourse being misrepresented. This finding appears to be linked to the limited volume of content these outlets have produced on feminist-related topics, suggesting a general reluctance rather than a deliberate framing. Although occasional misconceptions do surface, the role of these mainstream media accounts in actively shaping or reinforcing public misunderstanding of feminism seems limited. Instead, the primary sources of feminist misrepresentation are more likely

to originate from opinion-based content, influencer narratives, and audience-driven echo chambers as found in previous studies [13] [15]. These alternative sources often operate outside the norms of journalistic objectivity, allowing for greater distortion. Thus, while mainstream media on platform X may not be advancing feminist ideals, they are also not the central actors in spreading anti-feminist narratives.

6 Data Availability

All data generated and analyzed during this study are publicly available and can be accessed at the Google Scholar via the following link:
<https://scholar.google.com/>

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8 Authorship Statement

Annisa Dinara primarily responsible for the data analysis and the overall composition of the article. She conducted the critical review of relevant literature, processed the data, interpreted the findings, and wrote the original draft of the article.

Margynata Kurnia Putra contributed significantly to the initial conceptualization and development of the research idea. He provided intellectual guidance throughout the making of this article, and have detailed feedback during revision of the manuscript.

Both authors read the final results, and approved the final version for submission

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